

Synthesis, spectral, thermal, XRD and theoretical investigation of dimeric complexes with bis-bidentate ON-NO donor azodye ligand, 4,4'-(1*E*,1'*E*)-biphenyl-4,4'-diylbis(diazene-2,1-diyl)bis(4-nitrophenol)

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Abstract : The new azodye ligand 4,4'-(1*E*,1'*E*)-biphenyl-4,4'-diylbis(diazene-2,1-diyl)bis(4-nitrophenol) (BPDBDADBP) and its complexes of the type $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$, $\{M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}\}$ and $[M'_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$, $\{M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}\}$ were synthesized. The ligand and the complexes were characterized by elemental analytical, conductivity measurement, magnetic moments (RT), IR, electronic spectra, ESR, NMR, TG, DTA and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) spectra and theoretical (DFT/B3LYP) studies. The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are found to be octahedral, Cu^{II} complexes are distorted octahedral and Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are suggested to be tetrahedral stereochemistry. The thermal analysis data provided the kinetic parameters as order of decomposition reaction, activation energy and frequency factor. All theoretical calculations of the ligand and the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were made using GAUSSIAN 03 rev. A.01 programme package hybrid DFT/B3LYP hybrid functional level of theory with LANL2DZ basic set for copper and zinc atoms in gas phase and 6-31G(d,p) basic set for other atoms. The DFT study of the ligand and the complexes is used to calculate the bond length, bond angle, dihedral angle, HOMO, LUMO and dipole moment values. The calculated HOMO-LUMO energy gap shows that a charge transfer occurs within the molecule. The calculated value of zero point energy indicates that the stability of the metal complexes is greater than the ligand. The XRD data reveals that Zn^{II} complex is found to have a monoclinic crystal system.

Keywords : Azodye complexes, dimeric complexes, theoretical study (DFT/B3LYP).

Introduction

The study of azodyes and their dimeric complexes has gained much importance in recent years because of their wide range of applications in the field of chemotherapeutics¹ as drugs chemical laboratories as indicator, chemical reactions as catalyst² and photo sensors³, food industries^{4,5} as preservative and in textile industries as dyeing agent. In continuation to our earlier works^{6,7}, the present study reports the synthesis and characterization of a new tetradentate ligand, namely 4,4'-(1*E*,1'*E*)-biphenyl-4,4'-diylbis(diazene-2,1-diyl)bis(4-nitrophenol) (BPDBDADBP) (Fig. 1) and its metal complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} . The study also includes structural elucidation of the above complexes by conventional methods, supported by computational study (DFT/B3LYP) of the ligand and its complexes and their thermal, NMR, ESR and XRD studies.

2,2'-(1*E*,1'*E*)-Biphenyl-4,4'-diylbis(diazene-2,1-diyl)bis(4-nitrophenol)

Fig. 1. A novel tetradentate oxygen-nitrogen donor azodye ligand was made in this study.

Experimental

Materials :

The chemicals benzidine and *p*-nitrophenol were E. Merck grade. The chlorides of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} were of S.R.L. grade. All other reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and were of analytical grade.

Synthesis of the azo dye ligand :

The azo dye ligand was prepared by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chloride obtained from benzidine (0.01 mol, 1.71 g) with an alkaline solution of *p*-nitrophenol (0.02 mol, 2.78 g) respectively at 0–5 °C.

Synthesis of the metal complexes :

The metal chlorides in ethanol were mixed separately with ethanolic solution of the ligand LH₂ in 2 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting solutions were heated to 60–70 °C for about one hour on a heating mantle. The solution was then cooled down to room temperature and the pH was raised to ~7 by adding concentrated NH₄OH drop by drop with stirring. The solid complexes thus formed were then washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis (C, H, N and Cl) were carried out on elemental analyser Perkin-Elmer 2400 while metals were determined by EDTA after decomposing the complexes with conc. HNO₃. Conductance measurements of the complexes were made using Toshniwal CL 01-06 Conductivity Bridge. The magnetic susceptibility were made at RT by Gouy method using Hg[Co(CN)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra (KBr pellet) were recorded using IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in DMF were recorded on a Hilger-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer, ESR spectra of Cu^{II} complex was recorded on a E₄-spectrometer and NMR spectra on a Jeol GSX 400 with DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent and TMS as internal standard. X-Ray diffraction (powder pattern) of the Ni^{II} complex was recorded on a Phillips PW 1130/00 diffractometer with scan axis-Gonio, start position (2θ–10.004) end position (2θ–89.976) anode material CuK-Alpha 1 [Å] = 1.54060 and the generator settings 30 mA, 40 KV. The TG, DTG and DTA of the

complex is recorded on NETZSCH STA 409 C/CD in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C per minute.

Theoretical (DFT/B3LYP) studies :

The input file of ligand, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared with Gauss View 5.0.8⁸. All theoretical calcula-

tions of the ligand and the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were made using GAUSSIAN 03 rev. A.01 programme package^{9–15} hybrid DFT/B3LYP hybrid functional level of theory with LANL2DZ basic set for copper and zinc atoms in gas phase and 6-31G(d,p) basic set for other atoms. The 6-31G(d,p) is the most popular and appropriate basic set that explains p function to all hydrogen atoms in addition to that d function for other heavy atom and LANL2DZ basic set is suitable to all first row transition metal because it uses the calculation of effective core potential surfaces.

Results and discussion

The metal complexes were prepared according to the following reaction scheme :

where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, LH₂ = BPDBDADBP

where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, LH₂ = BPDBDADBP

The physical characteristics, micro analytical and molar conductance data of the ligand and the metal complexes are given in Table 1. The analytical data of the complexes revealed 2 : 1 molar ratio (Metal : Ligand) and correspond

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the ligand and its complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			M	C	H	N	Cl	
1.	LH ₂	Brown	–	59.2 (59.51)	3.1 (3.33)	17.1 (17.35)	–	–
2.	[Co ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Faint brown	14.8 (15.13)	36.4 (36.99)	3.2 (3.36)	10.5 (10.78)	8.9 (9.1)	5.2
3.	[Ni ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Grey	14.9 (15.07)	36.6 (37.01)	3.1 (3.37)	10.5 (10.79)	8.9 (9.1)	3.1
4.	[Cu ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Faint green	15.8 (16.12)	36.2 (36.56)	3.2 (3.32)	10.2 (10.66)	8.7 (8.99)	1.7
5.	[Zn ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Faint pink	17.9 (18.16)	39.8 (40.03)	2.4 (2.52)	11.4 (11.67)	9.6 (9.85)	–
6.	[Cd ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	White	27.2 (27.61)	35.1 (35.41)	2.1 (2.23)	10.1 (10.32)	8.5 (8.71)	–
7.	[Hg ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Grey	40.1 (40.5)	28.7 (29.1)	1.7 (1.83)	8.2 (8.48)	6.9 (7.16)	–

LH₂ = 4,4'-(1*E*,1'*E*)-biphenyl-4,4'-diylbis(diazene-2,1-diyl)bis(4-nitrophenol) (BPDBDADBP).

well with the general formula [M₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆], [M'₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂] where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}; M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; LH₂ = C₂₄H₁₆N₆O₆ (Calcd. (%) : C, 59.51; H, 3.33; N, 17.35; O, 19.82. Found (%) : C, 59.6; H, 3.5; N, 17.5; O, 19.7). All the complexes are semi-crystalline in nature having high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents as methanol, ethanol and benzene but soluble in dimethylformamide. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from the low conductance values (4.2–5.4 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in 10⁻³ M DMF solution.

Spectroscopic data :

Infrared spectra :

In the IR spectrum of the ligand, broad band is observed at 3350 cm⁻¹ (LH₂) that may be attributed to intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding. The absence of this band in the spectra of the metal complexes indicates deprotonation of the phenolic -OH groups and bonding of phenolic oxygen atom to the metal ion¹⁶. This is further supported by the shift of the band at 1455 cm⁻¹ to 1400 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes. The sharp band of the ligand appearing at 1580 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to ν_(-N=N-) vibration and in the metal chelates these bands are shown at ~1645–1650 cm⁻¹, that indicates the coordination of one of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions¹⁷. In the metal complexes broad band appears at ~3320–3340 cm⁻¹ followed by sharp peaks at ~850 cm⁻¹ and ~700 cm⁻¹ assignable to -OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations, respectively indicating the presence of co-ordinated water molecules in the complexes¹⁸. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligand to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of bands at ~515 cm⁻¹ (M–O) and ~450 cm⁻¹ (M–N)¹⁹.

Electronic spectra :

In the electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex, four ligand field bands appear at 8265, 16690, 20335 and 32450 cm⁻¹.

The first three bands can be attributed to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions, respectively and the fourth band is assigned to a CT band. The ligand field parameters as $Dq = 842.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 815.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta_{35} = 0.839 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.019$ and $\sigma = 19.18\%$ suggest an octahedral geometry for the complex^{20,21}. In the electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex, four ligand field bands are observed at 10235, 17385, 24990 and 32670 cm⁻¹ assignable to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂), → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) and CT transition, respectively in an octahedral geometry. The ligand field parameters as $Dq = 1023.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 778 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta_{35} = 0.747 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.698$ and $\sigma = 33.87\%$ can confirm an octahedral configuration for the complex. The electronic spectrum of the copper(II) complex exhibits one broad band at ~13340–14485 cm⁻¹ with maxima at ~14370 cm⁻¹ assignable to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition in support of a distorted-octahedral configuration of the complex^{22,23}.

Powder XRD studies :

The XRD (powder pattern) of the complex [Zn₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂] was indexed in X-ray diffractometer with Cu as anode material, K-alpha [Å] = 1.54060 and the generator settings 30 mA, 40 KV. The prominent peaks (Graph 3) of the diffraction pattern were indexed and analysed by the computer programme LSUCRPC²⁴. The lattice parameters *a*, *b*, *c*, α , β , γ and *V* (volume) are shown in Table 2 along with miceller indices *h k l*. The indexing is confirmed by comparing with observed and calculated 2θ values that is evident from the figure of merit 8.4 as suggested by de Woulff²⁵. The observed and calculated 2θ values are also in good agreement. The density (*d*) of the complex was determined by the flotation method in a saturated solution of KBr, NaCl and benzene separately. The number of formula units per unit cell (*n*) is calculated from the relation

$$n = dNV/M$$

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of the complex

Observed 2θ	Calculated 2θ	d-spacing	h k l	Difference (2θ)
11.61	11.59	7.629	1 1 0	0.02
21.52	21.46	4.137	0 0 1	0.06
22.57	22.56	3.939	2 0 0	0.01
24.47	24.46	3.636	1 1 1	0.01
32.62	32.60	2.744	2 8 0	0.02
34.27	34.25	2.616	3 1 0	0.02
40.07	40.02	2.251	3 7 0	0.05
45.97	45.90	1.975	1 15 0	0.07
46.26	46.21	1.963	1 3 2	0.05
52.87	52.81	1.732	4 4 1	0.06
58.77	58.75	1.570	3 5 2	0.02
65.05	65.02	1.433	1 21 0	0.03
70.37	70.34	1.337	1 4 3	0.03
76.22	76.20	1.248	5 13 1	0.02
80.34	80.31	1.195	4 14 2	0.03

$a = 7.972 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, Volume = 904.35 \AA^3 , Bravais lattice = P, $b = 19.193 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 100.066^\circ$, Density = 2.74 g/cm^3 , Figure of merit = 8.4, $c = 6.003 \text{ \AA}$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$, Number of unit cell (n) = 2, Crystal system = Monoclinic.

where d = density of the compound, N = Avogadro's number, V = volume of the unit cell and M = molecular weight of the complex. The value of 'n' is found to be '2' that agrees well with the suggested triclinic structure of the complexes. The mean particle size of the same complex can be measured from the Debye Scherrer equation

$$D = K\lambda/\beta \cos\theta$$

where D = particle size, K = dimensionless shape factor, λ = X-ray wavelength, β = line broadening at half the maximum intensity, θ = diffraction angle. This equation relates the size of the particle in a solid in the broadening of a peak in a diffraction pattern. The particle size of the complex $[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ is found to be 11.5 nm^{26} .

¹H NMR studies :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand LH₂ was recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ solvent. The peak observed at δ 6.4 ppm corresponds to fourteen phenyl protons²⁷. The presence of phenolic proton (OH) was observed at δ 8.1 ppm. (Graph 1).

ESR studies :

The ESR spectrum of the copper complex $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2]$

Graph 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of LH₂.

Graph 4. TGA of $[\text{Cd}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

tween 600 °C–700 °C supported by endothermic peak at 600 °C. Finally, the thermogram becomes a straight line after 700 °C.

Freeman-Carroll method was used to calculate kinetic parameters as order of the reaction (n) and activation energy (E_a)³¹. The equation used for this purpose is

$$-dW/dt = R_T = Z/R_H e^{-E_a/RT} W^n$$

where R_H = rate of heating, W = weight fraction of the reacting material, E_a = activation energy and Z = frequency factor. This equation in the difference form can be written as

$$\Delta \log R_T = n \Delta \log W - E_a/2.303 R \Delta(1/T)$$

when $\Delta(1/T)$ is kept constant a plot of $\Delta \log R_T$ versus $\Delta \log W$ gives a linear relationship whose slope and intercept provide the value of n and E_a respectively. The order of decomposition reaction and the activation energy are found to be 1.5 and 4.8 J/mole, respectively. The autocatalytic effect of the metal ion on the decomposition reaction explains the ion value of activation energy³². The correlation factor (r) is found to be 0.96 and the thermal

decomposition of the complex fits well with the experimental results. The complex is found to be stable upon 700 °C that suggests non-volatile nature of the complex.

Theoretical calculation :

The ligand (LH_2) and its complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ and $[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ were optimized at B3LYP/6.31G(d,p) and B3LYP/LANL2DZ levels in gas phase. The Fig. 2 shows the optimized molecular structure and atomic numbering scheme for ligand and Figs. 3 and 4 show the same for the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively. Some structural parameters of the ligand and the complexes as bond length and bond angle are listed in Tables 3 and 4. The bond lengths in the metal complexes are found to be different from the same bond length of the free ligand that suggest coordination of the metal ion with the ligand. The bond angles around the copper ion are close to 90°. So, distorted octahedral geometry is suggested for the copper complex. Similarly the bond angles in the zinc complex is found to be close to 109° and hence distorted tetrahedral geometry may be suggested for the above complex^{33,34}.

Fig. 2. Optimised geometry of the ligand LH₂.

Fig. 3. Optimised geometry of the Cu^{II} complex with LH₂.

Fig. 4. Optimised geometry of the Zn^{II} complex with LH₂.

Table 3. Selected bond length (Å) and bond angle (degree) of the ligand (LH₂)

B3LYP/6.31G(d,p)	
Bond length (Å)	Bond angle (°)
N8-N9 (1.2480)	C11-N9-N8 (120.0043)
C5-C6 (1.3368)	C8-C5-C6 (120.0168)
C6-O7 (1.3550)	C5-C6-O7 (119.9787)
N9-C11 (1.2598)	N9-N8-C5 (120.0043)
C5-N8 (1.2598)	

The calculation of single point energy and dipole moment of the ligand and Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were made by using DFT/B3LYP 6.31G(d,p) and DFT/B3LYP LANL2DZ basic sets. The single point energy (kcal/mol) and the dipole moment (*D*) of the ligand (LH₂) as calculated by DFT/B3LYP 6.31G(d,p) method are found to be -1.0688×10^6 and 0.00247 respectively. Similarly single point energy (kcal/mol) and dipole moment (*D*) values as calculated by DFT/B3LYP 6.31G(d,p) and DFT/B3LYP LANL2DZ methods of the complexes [Cu₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆] are found to be -3.9594×10^6 , -1.5870×10^6 , 3.7834, 4.1286 and [Zn₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂] -4.1070×10^6 , -1.3975×10^6 , 0.4577, 1.0286. From the above data it is observed that the lowering of the single point energy values take place in the metal complexes compared to the ligand which confirms that the complexes are more stable than the ligand. The higher dipole moment values of the complexes than the ligand show stronger dipole-dipole interaction after complexation.

The determination of energy for the HOMO (π donor) and LUMO (π acceptor) are two important parameters in quantum chemical calculations. The HOMO (Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital) is mainly act as an electron donor and LUMO (Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital) act as an electron acceptor. The E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} energy of the ligand and its Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are computed from the optimized geometry. Global reactivity indices as electronegativity (χ), chemical potential (μ), global hardness (η), global softness (*S*) and global electrophilicity index (ω) are given below^{36,37}.

$$\chi = \frac{(E_{\text{LUMO}} + E_{\text{HOMO}})}{2}$$

$$\mu = -\chi = \frac{(E_{\text{LUMO}} + E_{\text{HOMO}})}{2}$$

$$\eta = \frac{(E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}})}{2}$$

$$S = \frac{1}{2\eta}$$

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta}$$

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\eta}$$

The quantum chemical parameters as HOMO (eV), LUMO (eV), ΔE (eV), χ (Pauling), η (eV), σ , μ (eV), S and ω (eV) of the ligand (LH₂) are found to be -5.320, -3.123,

2.197, 4.221, 1.098, 0.910, -4.221, 0.455, 8.112 and the complexes [Cu₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆] -4.534, -3.803, 0.731, 4.168, 0.365, 2.739, -4.168, 1.369, 23.797 and [Zn₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂] -5.023, -4.253, 0.770, 4.638, 0.385, 2.597, -4.638, 1.298, 27.936. It is observed from the global reactivity parameters that the electrophilicity value of the ligand 8.112, Cu^{II} 23.797 and Zn^{II} 27.936 complex that the reactivity order is ligand > Cu^{II} complex > Zn^{II} complex according to minimum electrophilicity principle. The energy gap between E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} is an important parameter to determine the chemical reactivity and chemical stability of the molecule³⁵. It is known that a small energy

Table 4. Selected bond length (Å) and bond angle (degree) of [Cu₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆] and [Zn₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂]

[Cu ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆] B3LYP/LANL2DZ		[Zn ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] B3LYP/LANL2DZ	
Bond length (Å)	Bond angle (°)	Bond length (Å)	Bond angle (°)
N8-N9 (1.2481)	C31-N9-N8 (122.9394)	N8-N9 (1.2479)	C31-N9-N8 (112.1316)
C5-C6 (1.3370)	Cu31-O7-C6 (109.5162)	C5-C6 (1.3370)	Zn31-O7-C6 (109.5067)
C6-O7 (1.3551)	O7-Cu31-Cl34 (116.3337)	C6-O7 (1.3551)	O7-Zn31-Cl34 (123.7614)
N9-C11 (1.2600)	N9-Cu31-O7 (97.4975)	N9-C11 (1.2594)	N9-Zn31-O7 (95.5743)
C5-N8 (1.2601)	N9-Cu31-O32 (112.3555)	C5-N8 (1.2601)	N9-Zn31-O32 (132.2136)
Cu31-N9 (1.3650)		Zn31-N9 (1.8246)	
Cu31-O7 (1.8099)		Zn31-O7 (1.8901)	
Cu31-Cl34 (2.1606)		Zn31-Cl34 (2.2401)	
Cu31-O32 (1.8098)		Zn31-O32 (1.8900)	

Fig. 5. Molecular orbital energy level diagram with HOMO and LUMO orbital of LH₂.

Fig. 6. Molecular orbital energy level diagram with HOMO and LUMO orbital of Cu^{II} complex.

Fig. 7. Molecular orbital energy level diagram with HOMO and LUMO orbital of Zn^{II} complex.

gap between E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} is found to be more polarized and is known as soft molecule that is more reac-

tive than the hard molecule as it easily offers electrons to the acceptor. When the energy gap is small, charge trans-

fer occurs easily between two levels. The high value of ΔE indicates that the ligand molecule has high inclination to bind with a metal ion. The E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} plots and the molecular orbital energy level diagram (Figs. 5, 6 and 7) of the ligand LH_2 and its complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ and $[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ show the exact energy gap between these two orbitals. Both the complexes may be used as better conductor because the energy gap between E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} is small.

Conclusion

In summary, a novel tetradentate ligand, 4,4'-(1*E*,1'*E*)-biphenyl-4,4'-diylbis(diazene-2,1-diyl)bis(4-nitrophenol) and its six dimeric stable complexes were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, IR, electronic, ^1H NMR and ESR spectra. The stability of the complexes was explained and kinetic parameters as order of the reaction (n) and activation energy (E_a) were calculated by using Freeman-Carroll method. From the XRD (powder pattern) study, the lattice parameters of the $[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex have been calculated that belongs to monoclinic crystal system. The theoretical study of the ligand LH_2 and its Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes reveals the bonding of the ligand with the metal ions forming stable complexes, supported by their quantum chemical parameters.

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